

THE IMPACT OF BODY MASS INDEX ON ARTERIAL BLOOD PRESSURE PARAMETERS IN PATIENTS WITH ESSENTIAL ARTERIAL HYPERTENSION: RESULTS OF A PROSPECTIVE STUDY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15459209>

Abstract. *The aim of this prospective study was to investigate the relationship between body mass index (BMI) and blood pressure (BP) parameters in 171 patients with essential arterial hypertension (EAH) and/or obesity. Patients with EAH were stratified into three groups based on BMI and history of EAH. It was found that patients with EAH and obesity exhibited higher BP values compared to those without EAH. The results highlight the need for personalized approaches to the treatment of EAH, taking BMI into account.*

Keywords: *essential hypertension, body mass index, blood pressure, obesity, antihypertensive therapy.*

Introduction. Essential arterial hypertension (EAH) is considered to be a major risk factor for cardiovascular mortality. According to data from the landmark CALIBER study, which encompassed 1.25 million individuals, EAH can significantly increase the risk of the development of subsequent cardiovascular disease (CVD). In EAH, the risk for development of CVD by age 30 is 63.3% compared to 46.1% in those with normal arterial blood pressure (ABP). The risk of complications such as stroke, myocardial infarction and chronic heart failure is proportional to systolic arterial blood pressure (SABP) levels [8].

In Uzbekistan, EAH is in a more or less similar situation. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) report "Prevention and Control of Non-Communicable Diseases in Uzbekistan" (2018), CVD related to hypertension is responsible for 63.3% of all cases of mortality. The main complications from EAH, like myocardial infarction and stroke, affect people of working age. There are high social and economic losses, so it is critical to address the burden of non-communicable diseases. While WHO's recommendations on prevention and treatment for CVD have been adopted, access to antihypertensive therapy is limited. This limited access creates poor ABP control, high mortality from CVD, and substantial economic losses. All of which are exacerbated by EAH [1, 6].

Methodology. The Eurasian clinical recommendations indicate that global obesity prevalence has increased almost two times in the last 30 years, with an increasing average body mass index (BMI) by 0.4–0.5 kg/m² each decade (Chazova IE et al., 2022) [4]. It has also been documented that obesity can affect the growth of CVD, even when other conventional risk factors (like hypertension or diabetes) are not present [5]. Since adolescents and young adults have been shown in recent scientific evidence to have a predominant role of obesity in developing EAH and causing long-term harm. The development of obesity and hypertension in earlier 'life' stages may be thought of as a constellation of perinatal programming, and indicates the important role of

genetic polymorphisms in the pathogenic mechanics of obesity-related hypertension [7]. Additionally, the pathological growth of systemic-complexes and insulin resistance can worsen the intervening cardiometabolic changes to disease worsening [2, 3].

By examining the relationship between BMI and ABP parameters in patients with EAH, regardless of whether they are obese, and assessing the efficacy of antihypertensive therapy based on clinical-anamnestic characteristics and obesity levels, the study aims to support the need for individualised treatment.

Study resources and techniques: The main cohort of the study consisted of 171 participants who were divided into three comparative subgroups. A multi-phase, structured clinical and instrumental evaluation was performed on each participant. The purpose of the study was to thoroughly assess the patients' overall somatic condition and to pinpoint important predictors of EAH development. In the first step, a thorough medical history was gathered, a family history of cardiovascular diseases was evaluated, known risk factors were identified, and behavioural patterns that could have a negative impact on health were examined. These included dietary patterns, levels of physical activity, exposure to chronic stress, and harmful habits (such as smoking and alcohol consumption). ABP, heart rate (HR), and basic anthropometric measurements (height, body weight, and waist circumference) were recorded during the clinical and physical examination that followed. BMI was then computed to evaluate risk levels associated with obesity. A standardised electronic medical record system was created in order to standardise and organise the data that was gathered. These documents ensured a thorough clinical-diagnostic approach at every stage of the study by compiling laboratory and instrumental data, medical history, and physical examination results.

Results and discussion of the study. Based on whether or not they had an EAH diagnosis and their BMI as determined by the Kettle formula, all 171 patients who were part of the main observation cohort were divided into three clinical-anamnestic subgroups. Group I comprised 57 patients (33.4%) with an average BMI of 25.45 ± 1.82 kg/m², who were diagnosed with EAH and had normal anthropometric parameters. Group II included 59 patients (34.5%) with EAH who were overweight or in some degree of obesity, with an average BMI of 32.93 ± 2.36 kg/m². Group III included 55 patients (32.1%) with an average BMI of 34.73 ± 1.65 kg/m² who had no history of EAH but showed clear symptoms of alimentary-constitutional obesity.

105 (90.6%) of the 116 patients in clinical subgroups I and II (100%) had an EAH diagnosis that had been previously verified. Group I experienced an average disease duration of 9.12 ± 1.75 years, while Group II experienced an average disease duration of 10.59 ± 1.80 years. With an average disease duration of 2.2 ± 0.06 months in group I and 1.8 ± 0.12 months in group II at the time of study inclusion, the remaining 11 patients (9.4%) had a new diagnosis of EAH (Table 1). Antihypertensive medication was given to 103 patients (88.79%) with EAH grades I–III in the chosen sample. Among the medications were β -blockers, calcium antagonists, diuretics, and renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) blockers.

Nevertheless, none of the groups under analysis achieved the desired ABP levels. Just 6 patients (5.1%) were able to achieve adequate control of their blood pressure with optimal doses of antihypertensive medications: 5.2% in group I and 5% in group II. Thirteen patients (11.2%) (10.6% in group I, 12% in group II) and 97 patients (83.6%) (84.2%) had uncontrolled hypertension.

The next step involved analyzing the main cohort's (groups I, II, and III) average ABP values according to BMI. Only average ABP readings were taken into account because group III

included obese patients without a history of EAH. The association between body weight, obesity level, and systolic (SABP) and diastolic (DABP) ABP parameters was thoroughly examined using statistical analysis based on the data shown in Table 2.

Group I data analysis showed that the average DABP was 93.75 ± 2.85 mm Hg and the average SABP was 154.37 ± 7.95 mm Hg. Patients in this group with normal BMI (<25 kg/m², n=16,28%) showed a DABP of 98.00 ± 3.32 mmHg and a SABP of 162.67 ± 8.76 mmHg when stratified by BMI. On the other hand, the SABP of 151.40 ± 7.44 mm Hg and the DABP of 92.24 ± 2.48 mm Hg of patients who were overweight (BMI 25–29.99 kg/m², n=41, 72%) were higher than the group average.

A closer look at group II, which included patients with both obesity and EAH, revealed an average DABP of 93.05 ± 3.60 mm Hg and an average SABP of 155.68 ± 6.76 mm Hg. Patients in this group with a BMI between 30 and 34.99 kg/m² (n=38, 64.4%) had a DABP of 93.42 ± 3.78 mm Hg and a SABP of 154.34 ± 4.05 mm Hg. The SABP rose to 159.38 ± 6.39 mm Hg and the DABP was 91.88 ± 3.45 mm Hg in patients with a BMI of 35–39.99 kg/m² (n=16, 27.1%). Lastly, the SABP was 154.00 ± 6.52 mm Hg and the DABP was 94.00 ± 3.03 mm Hg in patients with a BMI >40 kg/m² (n=5, 8.5%).

With an average SABP of 125.38 ± 3.06 mm Hg and an average DABP of 74.64 ± 3.37 mm Hg, group III, which comprised patients with obesity but no EAH, had significantly lower ABP values, according to analysis. However, when patients were categorised by their level of obesity (BMI), a distinct trend towards elevated ABP was noted, even though these values were within the average range.

Table 1. Distribution of patients in the main cohort by EAH duration and level of therapy control (n=116)

Duration of EAH	group I (n=57)	group II (n=59)
newly diagnosed EAH	5 (8,8 %)	6 (10,1 %)
men, n (%)	2 (40 %)	1 (16,7 %)
women, n (%)	3 (60 %)	5 (83,3 %)
diagnosed EAH	52 (91,2 %)	53 (89,9 %)
men, n (%)	26 (50 %)	21 (39,7 %)
women, n (%)	26 (50 %)	32 (60,3 %)
control of EAH treatment	group I (n=57)	group II (n=59)
uncontrolled, n (%)	6 (10,6 %)	7 (12 %)
men, n (%)	2 (33,3 %)	3 (42,9 %)
women, n (%)	4 (66,7 %)	4 (57,1 %)
inadequate control, n (%)	48 (84,2 %)	49 (83 %)
men, n (%)	25 (52 %)	19 (38,8 %)
women, n (%)	23 (48 %)	30 (61,2 %)
controlled, n (%)	3 (5,2 %)	3 (5 %)
men, n (%)	1 (33,3 %)	2 (67 %)
women, n (%)	2 (66,7 %)	1 (33 %)

Significant differences between the second and third groups were found through comparative analysis and statistical confirmation. In particular, patients with a BMI between 30 and 34.99 kg/m² (n=35, 63.6%) had a SABP of 124.22 ± 3.05 mm Hg ($p<0.01$), while group II had a SABP of 154.34 ± 4.05 mm Hg. SABP rose to 127.29 ± 2.64 mm Hg ($p<0.01$) in the group with a BMI of 35–39.99 kg/m² (n=14, 25.4%) as opposed to group II: 159.38 ± 6.39 mm Hg. SABP

and DABP increased to 127.00 ± 3.78 mm Hg ($p < 0.05$, compared to group II: 154.00 ± 6.52 mm Hg) and 80.83 ± 1.85 mm Hg ($p < 0.05^*$, compared to group II: 94.00 ± 3.03 mm Hg) respectively for patients with a BMI > 40 kg/m² ($n=6$, 11%).

Table 2. Average blood pressure values in the main cohort, stratified by BMI ($n=171$)

	SABP, mm.Hg	DABP, mm.Hg
group I (n=57)	154,37±7,95	93,75±2,85
BMI < 25 kg/m ² , $\Pi=16$ (28%)	162,67±8,76	98,00±3,32
BMI 25-29,99 kg/m ² , $\Pi=41$ (72%)	151,40±7,44	92,24±2,48
group II (n=59)	155,68±6,76	93,05±3,60
BMI 30-34,99 kg/m ² , $\Pi=38$ (64,4%)	154,34±4,05**	93,42±3,78
BMI 35-39,99 kg/m ² , $\Pi=16$ (27,1%)	159,38±6,39**	91,88±3,45
BMI > 40 kg/m ² , $\Pi=5$ (8,5%)	154,00±6,52*	94,00±3,03*
group III (n=55)	125,38±3,06	74,64±3,37
BMI 30-34,99 kg/m ² , $\Pi=35$ (63,6%)	124,22±3,05**	73,75±3,57
BMI 35-39,99 kg/m ² , $\Pi=14$ (25,4%)	127,29±2,64**	73,21±3,46*
BMI > 40 kg/m ² , $\Pi=6$ (11%)	127,00±3,78*	80,83±1,85*

** $p < 0.01$ — statistically significant differences for BMI 30–34.99 and 35–39.99 kg/m²,
 $*p < 0.05$ — statistically significant differences for BMI > 40 kg/m².

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Conclusion. In patients with EAH, the prospective study found a significant correlation between BMI and ABP. The results showed that systolic and DABP values were higher in patients with EAH and normal BMI than in those who were overweight or obese. At the same time, individuals with obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m²) and EAH also exhibited a more pronounced rise in SABP, especially those with a BMI between 35 and 39.99 kg/m². Patients with a BMI greater than 40 kg/m² showed an average rise in ABP, mostly diastolic, in obese people without a history of EAH. The low effectiveness of antihypertensive medication (only 5.1% of patients achieved adequate ABP control) suggests that therapy optimisation was not sufficiently implemented across study groups. EAH significantly worsens ABP parameters in patients with similar BMI levels, according to comparative analysis. This highlights the need for individualised treatment plans that take into consideration both BMI and EAH status in order to improve clinical outcomes and ABP control.

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